

Universal criterion of divisibility of numbers

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I. Introduction

When finding divisors of a number, various divisibility criteria are employed. Sometimes, the use of multiple criteria can hinder the process of finding the divisors of a number. In this work, I aim to present a universal algorithm for finding divisors of numbers. The algorithm is capable of identifying all divisors of a number and can be beneficial for prime factorization of numbers. In my algorithm, there is a concept called "variable-base number system."

II. Explanation of the algorithm

Let's denote the divisor of the number as "d_i," and the value of the variable base as "s."

We can represent any number in the decimal number system as follows:

$$A = \sum_{i=0}^n 10^i a_i.$$

Important Condition: $d_i + s^i = 10^i$. Let's see few examples:

For $i = 1$ we have $d_1 + s = 10 \Rightarrow d_1 = 10 - s$

For $i = 2$ we have $d_2 + s^2 = 10^2 \Rightarrow d_2 = (10 - s)(10+s) = d_1(10+s)$

For $i = 3$ we have $d_3 + s^3 = 10^3 \Rightarrow d_3 = (10-s)(100+10s+s^2) = d_1(100+10s+s^2)$

.....

For $i = n$ we have $d_n + s^n = 10^n \Rightarrow d_n = (10-s)(10^{n-1}+10^{n-2}s+10^{n-3}s^2+\dots) = d_1(10^{n-1}+10^{n-2}s+10^{n-3}s^2+\dots)$

Conclusion: every d_i ($i \geq 1$) dividing by d_1 .

Let's write this expression using the condition $d_i + s^i = 10^i$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } A &= \sum_{i=0}^n 10^i a_i = a_0 + 10a_1 + 100a_2 + 1000a_3 + \dots + 10^i a_i + \dots = a_0 + (d_1 + s)a_1 + (d_2 + s^2)a_2 + (d_3 + s^3)a_3 + \dots + (d_n + s^n)a_n + \dots \\ &= a_0 + d_1 a_1 + s a_1 + d_2 a_2 + s^2 a_2 + d_3 a_3 + s^3 a_3 + \dots + d_n a_n + s^n a_n + \dots \\ &= (d_1 a_1 + d_2 a_2 + d_3 a_3 + \dots + d_n a_n + \dots) + (a_0 + s a_1 + s^2 a_2 + s^3 a_3 + s^n a_n + \dots) \\ &= (d_1 a_1 + d_1(10+s)a_2 + d_1(100+10s+s^2)a_3 + \dots + d_1(10^{n-1}+10^{n-2}s+10^{n-3}s^2+\dots)a_n + \dots) + (a_0 + s a_1 + s^2 a_2 + s^3 a_3 + s^n a_n + \dots) \\ &= d_1 [a_1 + (10+s)a_2 + (100+10s+s^2)a_3 + (10^{n-1}+10^{n-2}s+10^{n-3}s^2+\dots)a_n] + (a_0 + s a_1 + s^2 a_2 + s^3 a_3 + s^n a_n + \dots) \end{aligned}$$

We have 2 cases:

- 1) $(a_0 + sa_1 + s^2a_2 + s^3a_3 + s^na_n + \dots) = 0$. In this case, our number is definitely divisible by d_1 .
- 2) $(a_0 + sa_1 + s^2a_2 + s^3a_3 + s^na_n + \dots) \neq 0$. In this case, the sum must be divisible by d_1 .

Criterion: The number is divisible by d_1 if and only if $(a_0 + sa_1 + s^2a_2 + s^3a_3 + s^na_n + \dots)$ is divisible by d_1 .

The concept of variable base for a numeral system was discussed above. Let's see the simple examples:

$$135 \rightarrow 1 \times s^2 + 3 \times s + 5$$

$$12348 \rightarrow 1 \times s^4 + 2 \times s^3 + 3 \times s^2 + 4 \times s + 8$$

.....

Let's consider using of the algorithm:

Let's take the number 77:

- 1) Let's assume that 7 is a divisor of the number 77. So, we have $d_1 = 7$

Using condition we have $d_1 + s = 10 \Rightarrow 7 + s = 10 \Rightarrow s = 3$.

$$77 \rightarrow 7 \times s + 7 = 7 \times 3 + 7 = 28$$

We can repeat our iterations:

$$28 \rightarrow 2 \times s + 8 = 2 \times 3 + 8 = 14$$

$$14 \rightarrow s + 4 = 3 + 4 = 7$$

We have: 7, 14, 28. We can see that every number is divisible by 7. Therefore, 77 is divisible by 7

- 2) Let's assume that 11 is a divisor of the number 77. We have $11 + s = 10 \Rightarrow s = -1$

$77 \rightarrow 7 \times s + 7 = 7 \times (-1) + 7 = 0$. We can see that 0 is divisible by 7. Therefore, 77 is divisible by 11

We have 2 dividers: 7 and 11

- 3) Let's assume that 5 is a divisor of the number 77. We have $5 + s = 10 \Rightarrow s = 5$

$$77 \rightarrow 7 \times s + 7 = 7 \times 5 + 7 = 42$$

$$42 \rightarrow 4 \times s + 2 = 22$$

$$22 \rightarrow 2 \times s + 2 = 12$$

$$12 \rightarrow s + 2 = 7$$

We have: 7, 12, 22, 42. We can see that none of these numbers are divisible by 5 without a remainder. Therefore, 77 is not divisible by 5.

Let's take the number 5895:

Let's assume that 15 is a divisor of the number 5895. We have $15+s = 10 \Rightarrow s=-5$

$$5895 \rightarrow 5 \times s^3 + 8 \times s^2 + 9 \times s + 5 = -465$$

$$-465 \rightarrow -(4 \times s^2 + 6 \times s + 5) = -75$$

$$-75 \rightarrow -(7 \times s + 5) = 30$$

$$30 \rightarrow 3 \times s = -15$$

$$-15 \rightarrow -(s+5) = 0$$

We have: 0, -15, 30, -75, -465. All of these numbers are divisible by 15. Therefore, 5895 is divisible by 15.

We can use another way: The number is divisible by 15, when it is divisibly by 5 and 3.

Let's see that 3 is a divisor of the number 5895. We have $s = 7$

$$5895 \rightarrow 5 \times s^3 + 8 \times s^2 + 9 \times s + 5 = 2175$$

$$2175 \rightarrow 2 \times s^3 + s^2 + 7 \times s + 5 = 789$$

$$789 \rightarrow 7 \times s^2 + 8 \times s + 9 = 408$$

$$408 \rightarrow 4 \times s^2 + 8 = 204$$

$$204 \rightarrow 2 \times s^2 + 4 = 102$$

$$102 \rightarrow s^2 + 2 = 51$$

$$51 \rightarrow 5 \times s + 1 = 36$$

$$36 \rightarrow 3 \times s + 6 = 27$$

$$27 \rightarrow 2 \times s + 7 = 21$$

$$21 \rightarrow 2 \times s + 1 = 15$$

$$15 \rightarrow s + 5 = 12$$

$$12 \rightarrow s + 2 = 9$$

We have: 9, 12, 15, 21, 27, 36, 51, 102, 204, 408, 789, 2175. All these numbers are divisible by 3. Therefore, the number 5895 is divisible by 3.

Let's see that 5 is a divisor of the number 5895. We have $s = 5$

$$5895 \rightarrow 5 \times s^3 + 8 \times s^2 + 9 \times s + 5 = 875$$

$$875 \rightarrow 8 \times s^2 + 7 \times s + 5 = 240$$

$$240 \rightarrow 2 \times s^2 + 4 \times s = 70$$

$$70 \rightarrow 7 \times s = 35$$

$$35 \rightarrow 3 \times s + 5 = 20$$

$$20 \rightarrow 2 \times s = 10$$

$$10 \rightarrow s = 5$$

We have: 5, 10, 20, 35, 70, 240, 875. All these numbers are divisible by 5. Therefore, 5895 is divisible by 5.

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